

The JUGENE I/O Subsystem, its Architecture, Guidelines and Tools for Using it Efficiently

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Abstract

The I/O subsystems of high performance computing installations tend to be very system specific. There is only a loose coupling with compute architectures and consequently considerable freedom of choice in design and ample room for tradeoffs at various implementation levels. The PRACE Tier-0 systems are no exception in this respect. The I/O subsystem of JUGENE at the Forschungszentrum Jülich is not necessarily very similar to the I/O subsystems of IBM Blue Gene/P installations elsewhere. However, most applications that need efficient handling of petascale data cannot afford to ignore the I/O subsystem. To some extent system specific arrangements of resources need to be known to avoid system- or site-specific bottlenecks.

This first section of paper gives a fairly detailed description of the I/O subsystem of the PRACE Tier-0 system JUGENE at Jülich and points out what I/O rates that can be achieved maximally, following from the specifications of the components that have been used and the way they are interconnected.

In the second section, the description is complemented with some practical guidelines on how to do efficient I/O on JUGENE and a description of some tools for source level adaptation of applications for improving I/O performance. Using standard I/O and MPI communication, rather than adopting a particular library, variations on hierarchical organizing of I/O within an application are explored more in depth and compared for performance. Splitting a parallel program of multiple tasks into a number of equally sized I/O groups, in which a few tasks do I/O on behalf improves performance only moderately when group membership is determined rather arbitrarily. BlueGene specific MPI extensions can be used to bring topological information, about which tasks are being served by the same I/O node, into the program. Example programs are given on how these calls can be used to create a division into groups that are not only balanced in the IO/volume their produce, but also in the underlying resources they have at their disposal to handle the load.

1. The I/O subsystem

The I/O subsystem of JUGENE is a system of three hardware layers – with connectivity layers between them – show schematically in Figure 1. Within the Blue Gene/P itself there are a number of I/O nodes. These constitute the interface of the I/O subsystem to JUGENE’s computational resources. The I/O nodes act as shared file system clients. They do not contain any storage components themselves, nor do they connect to dedicated storage components that could be considered local to any particular I/O node.

For all file systems to which users have read and write access, IBM General Parallel File System (GPFS) technology is used. A cluster of file servers presents Network Storage Devices (NSD), to their clients. NSDs are the distributed shareable storage units from which GPFS file systems are built. Performing meta-data operations and responsibility for the shared file systems’ integrity is also the exclusive task of the cluster of the GPFS servers.

The GPFS NSDs use logical units (LUN) that are served by a storage back-end of storage controllers and disk enclosures. The storage controllers use hardware RAID technology to pack several physical disks into an aggregate LUN with enhanced performance as well as better protection against failure than each of the individual physical disks involved can provide on their own.

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I/O Figure 1: The three layers of the I/O subsystem schematically

1.1. nodes

I/O nodes of the Blue Gene/P are nodes dedicated to I/O that do not permit the user to run any tasks of the user’s parallel application. Each I/O node is connected via a 10 Gb/s Ethernet adapter to a network over which it accesses the GPFS shared file systems. This network, portrayed in Figure 1 as the yellow “file serving network connectivity layer”, is often referred to as “the functional network”.

The compute nodes, which run the application processes, do not have a connection to the functional network. Nevertheless, a user process can simply use I/O related system calls like `chdir()`, `open()`, `read()`, `write()`, or even `socket()`. “Under the hood” the compute node kernel (CNK) forwards all file system and socket related operations to an I/O node. This service is provided automatically and transparently by the CNK micro kernel.

Figure 2: I/O forwarding, or “function shipment” as IBM calls it, in more detail. The bi-directional red arrows show the typical path travelled by data associated with the function calls issued by an application process running on a compute node.

The I/O node is a small Linux system that can run several daemons. On the I/O node, the forwarded operations are handled by the control and I/O daemon (CIOD), which subsequently hands them to the appropriate component of the GPFS client software^b. The typical path travelled by data which is handed to and returned by I/O functions used by an application on a compute node, is presented schematically in Figure 2. IBM has aptly named this forwarding process *function shipment*, as the functionality provided by the I/O nodes is done via of implementation of runtime library functions and system calls, but *not via remote shell commands*.

Figure 2 also reveals the medium that is used within JUGENE for I/O forwarding as the “Global Tree”. This is a separate Blue Gene/P network that officially goes by the name of *global collective network*. It connects all nodes – compute and I/O nodes alike – with three links per node with a bandwidth of 6.8 Gb/s per link in both directions. The network has a tree-like topology in which any node can be viewed as the common top of three binary trees descending down to the other nodes. The routing protocol does not interrupt the CPU resources of the nodes. Conversely, neither the bandwidth nor the latency of these links is affected by the level of computational effort of the nodes it passes.

^b At least in the “normal” case, where GPFS file system access is concerned. But the I/O forwarding via the I/O nodes is not constrained to file system I/O. In principle the I/O node can also be used as a proxy to setup and UDP or TCP socket connection.

Figure 3: An I/O node with some of the topologically nearest compute nodes in its pset shown

Although the global collective network is indeed global and collective, the I/O nodes do *not* constitute a load sharing cluster. Compute nodes cannot forward to any I/O node, e.g. one that is less busy. The assignment of a set of compute nodes to their dedicated I/O node in the tree topology is completely static. It is determined by the number of I/O nodes plugged into a node board and the position of node boards with I/O nodes in a midplane. The aggregate I/O bandwidth at a jobs disposal will only grow if it is scaled up, run over more midplanes - and thus owns more I/O nodes. The set of compute nodes that share the same I/O node is usually called a *processor set* or *pset*. Figure 3 shows a pset from the perspective of an I/O node on top.

Collective message passing operations of a “one to all” nature use the global collective network as well. But since such operations are blocking, there cannot be any contention over the links in tree between message passing and I/O^c. Every node in the pset must go through one of the links of the connecting nodes a, b, or c directly to the I/O node. Since the aggregate bandwidth of these links is 20.4 Gb/s (bi-directional), the 10 Gb/s bandwidth of the I/O node’s Ethernet interface is rate limiting for I/O, as far as the pset is concerned.

JUGENE has a total of 600 I/O nodes. With the notable exception of one rack, *all I/O nodes are evenly distributed across the system with a fixed ratio of 1 I/O node per 128 compute nodes*. I.e.: 71 out of 72 JUGENE racks have 2 midplanes with 4 I/O nodes per midplane. This accounts for 568 I/O nodes. The remaining 32 I/O nodes are evenly distributed across the 2 midplanes of a single rack. Thus, this deviant rack (R87) has a much richer ratio of 1 I/O node per 32 compute nodes.

In the JUGENE production environment normal jobs are allocated at least a single midplane and thus jobs involve 2048 cores or a multiple thereof. Since it is not feasible to have a job without any I/O at all, the deviant rack is the only one that allows for computationally much smaller jobs – mainly for testing and debugging purposes. Note however that one has to be especially careful in inferring something about the scalability of a real user application on JUGENE with respect to its I/O behaviour from test runs solely conducted on this rack – precisely because of the higher I/O node to compute node ratio.

^c Unless the I/O operation itself would be asynchronous, but on Blue Gene/P File I/O cannot be. Attempts to use asynchronous I/O will result in run time errors. One IBM source that explicitly documents this, is the Blue Gene/P application development “RedBook” [1]. On JUGENE however, runtime errors are now avoided. A synchronous requests are silently treated and processed as synchronous

Since the assignment of I/O nodes to compute nodes is essentially fixed, the details reported above can be translated into Table 1, which summarizes theoretical maximum and average available I/O bandwidths at different levels of aggregation of computational resources. Although it is customary to report network bandwidths in terms of bits per second, the table reports them in Gigabytes or Megabytes per second as these are more convenient units for program tuning. The reported numbers are simply based on characteristics of the hardware configuration and assume that the I/O node internal processes (CIOD, mmfsd, etc.) that pass data to and from its network interface have no effect on the available bandwidth.

Actually achieved sustained I/O performance by applications will also depend on more or less balanced use of the I/O nodes, on the characteristics of the back-end to which the I/O node's interfaces connect, and on the way in which an application structures its requests in "chunks" that are more or less convenient for the back-end to handle – e.g. because they suit the file system block size of the addressed file system well.

Table 1: Theoretical maximum and average available bandwidths at various levels of aggregation of computational hardware resources.

Machine hardware unit	typical number of MPI tasks	Max. bandwidth	Avg. bandwidth
Normal production racks:			
midplane (512 compute nodes)	2048	5.00 GB/s	5.00 GB/s
<i>pset (128 compute nodes per I/O node)</i>	512	<i>1.25 GB/s</i>	<i>1.25 GB/s</i>
compute node	4	850 MB/s	10 MB/s
single core (typically runs 1 MPI task)	1	850 MB/s	2.5 MB/s
Testing rack only:			
midplane (512 compute nodes)	2048	20.00 GB/s	20.00 GB/s
<i>pset (32 compute nodes per I/O node)</i>	128	<i>1.25 GB/s</i>	<i>1.25 GB/s</i>
compute node	4	850 MB/s	40 MB/s
single core (typically runs 1 MPI task)	1	850 MB/s	10 MB/s

1.2. The file serving network layer

The GPFS clients on JUGENE's I/O nodes are served by a cluster of 24^d IBM p6-570 servers over the functional network. All servers are equipped with identical resources to access storage capacity on one side, and to communicate with their GPFS clients at the other side:

- 4 x 10 Gb/s Ethernet links into the functional network of the Blue Gene/P
- 8 x 4Gb/s Fibre Channel (FC4) host adapter ports

The maximum aggregate bandwidth that the servers can deliver together on this network is approximately 120 GB/s. At their "back-side" the servers are connected, via fibre channel, to storage boxes that in total can deliver a bandwidth of about 96GB/s. The latter is the smaller number, so the fibre channel connection and the performance of the storage boxes are decisive in what the I/O subsystem as a whole can deliver to the Blue Gene/P. The bandwidth of the functional network has some room to spare and is - in principle - no bottleneck.

Yet in practice it is, a little more intricate than that, because there is some oversubscription of the bandwidth available on the backplanes of the network switches. On the Ethernet side, all servers must to be able to talk all 600 I/O nodes. This cannot be solved by point to point cabling scheme. It requires some switching technology, but at present there is no – certainly no affordable – switching technology that is actually able to handle simultaneous switching of this amount of 10Gb/s Ethernet connections at wire speed.

The functional network of JUGENE consists of four fabrics, each with a Force10 E1200i switch with 224 10 Gb/s Ethernet ports. Even in these switches the sum bandwidth on all ports still exceeds the capacity that the backplane and forwarding engine can handle. Groups of four adjacent switch ports share a common path onto

^d Actually there are 24 data servers, plus 4 additional servers exclusively dedicated to serving file system meta-data.

the backplane and into the forwarding engine. Members of the same 4-port group are contending for the same bandwidth whenever two or more of them are concurrently handling traffic. So, theoretically there is a fourfold oversubscription on each of the four fabrics.

However, a number of heuristics with respect to traffic to be expected have been taken into account and have led to a strategy for the allocation of switch ports to interfaces that substantially reduces the probability that interfaces will actually be contending for the same bandwidth:

- The only traffic to be optimized is between servers and I/O nodes. The performance of traffic between I/O nodes, if it exists at all, is irrelevant.
- The GPFS servers are expected to be the busiest systems. The probability that most if not all servers are continuously concurrently engaged in I/O operations is very high.
- The probability of concurrent engagement in I/O operations is substantially higher for I/O nodes belonging to the same job than for I/O nodes belonging to different jobs. Concurrent I/O engagement of I/O nodes belonging to different jobs is accidental – and therefore incidental. Concurrent I/O engagement of I/O nodes belonging to the same job is a structural characteristic of many applications. So it is recurring rather than incidental.
- Jobs have a minimal size of one midplane containing four I/O nodes. Whenever possible, bigger jobs are scheduled on midplanes that are adjacent, or very near to each other, in terms of the topology of the Blue Gene/P internal 3D Torus network.

Working from these four tenets, the following port allocation strategy was developed and applied:

- Every GPFS/NSD server is directly linked to each of the four fabrics by plugging one of its interfaces into the first port of a 4-port group. This guarantees that no two GPFS/NSD server interfaces within the same fabric are ever competing for the same bandwidth.
- The four I/O nodes of a midplane are each hooked up to a different fabric. Thus, even the smallest jobs have the aggregate bandwidth of all four fabrics at their disposal.
- I/O nodes of neighbouring midplanes in the same fabric are distributed over different 4-port groups of the switch.

Because of the allocation strategy applied to server ports, it is plausible that there is never any contention for bandwidth among server ports. So the maximum aggregate bandwidth for all 24 servers simultaneously allowed by the network resources they have at their disposal, will indeed be close to 120 GB/s.

Figure 4: Logical model of port allocation on a fabric switch with 56 4-port groups. Each of the 56 groups has a 10 Gb/s bandwidth channel that is shared among its 4 members. The port allocation to I/O nodes, servers, front end nodes etc. is static – hard wired. The allocation of jobs to midplanes, and hence to the ports used by the I/O nodes of these midplanes, is dynamically determined by a batch scheduler.

Theoretically the minimum number of I/O nodes to mobilize this potential by acting as clients is 96 – i.e. 24 midplanes or 12 complete Blue Gene/P racks. But in practice it is likely to be higher, because this number assumes no contention between the clients at all. But one consequence of the above outlined strategy is that the probability of enlisting some I/O nodes that are competing for the same bandwidth increases when the number of I/O nodes increases. Increasing the number of I/O nodes certainly increases the effective bandwidth for a job - but with some decreasing *marginal* returns effect rather than in an entirely linear fashion. Moreover there will also be some quasi random effect caused by the allocation choices made by the batch system. One combination of midplanes may harbour a slightly smaller potential for contention than another one with the same number of midplanes.

Per fabric switch 24 ports are allocated to GPFS data servers and 4 additional are allocated to the 4 GPFS meta-data servers. Since these 28 ports are spread evenly across the 56 4-port groups, exactly half of the 4-port groups of a fabric switch have a server. It is very likely that the midplanes that are allocated to a port group shared with a server experience more contention for bandwidth than midplanes that are on a port group without a server connection. Identically sized jobs on JUGENE can have different I/O bandwidths at their disposal.

Figure 4 presents a logical model of the port allocation on a network switch used on the JUGENE functional network. Each of the 224 ports is represented by a square, and the squares are grouped in 56 groups. 142 unmarked green squares represent the connections of the midplanes of the production environment. Spreading them evenly across the available groups results 30 groups with 3 midplane connections and 26 groups with 2 midplane connections: $(30 \times 3) + (26 \times 2) = 142$. The light green squares, marked $a_1 - a_4$ and $b_1 - b_4$, represent the connections of the I/O nodes of the “deviant rack” (R87) described above. It shows that the bandwidth of these midplanes is also four times that of normal midplanes at the switch level. The yellow squares represent the GPFS server connections. The darker yellow ones, marked M1 – M4, represent the meta-data servers. The grey squares, marked with a question mark, are not necessarily empty. Some may also connect a front end node or some auxiliary systems not directly related to JUGENE at all. Some hypothetical jobs, A, B, and C, having a certain number of midplanes at their disposal, have been added to the picture. Other jobs would normally be running concurrently as well, using other midplanes, but are not shown.

Jobs A and C both utilize 16 midplanes. But at the switch level, the bandwidth of job A is much more likely to be “squeezed” than that of job C. The peak bandwidth that job A can achieve is about 80 Gb/s since it has only 8 channels at its disposal. Job C has 16 channels, hence its peak bandwidth at the switch is twice that of job A. Job C and job B would no doubt sometimes be contending over the bandwidths of channels 33 – 38. But such contention would be incidental, since the jobs are not likely to be continuously engaged in I/O. The I/O of the tasks within a job on the other hand is highly likely to be orchestrated and more or less simultaneous. So the tasks of job are likely to be contending among themselves for the bandwidths of channels 6 -13 when they – simultaneously –engage in I/O.

1.3. I/O servers and storage controllers: basic GPFS building blocks

At their “back-side” the servers are to IBM DS5300 dual controller storage boxes with expansion cabinets of disks. A DS5300 storage box has twelve 4Gb/s host ports - six per controller. Groups of three IBM p6-570 servers described previous section are combined with two DS5300 storage boxes in such a way that each of the servers can access every LUN exported by the storage boxes over every controller. This conglomerate of resources is used as a basic building block for the construction of GPFS file systems, and is shown schematically in Figure 5. Within a building block there are multiple connections between components, not just to add performance, but also a fair level of fault tolerance.

A building block contains 72 RAID6 LUNs. The segment size of the LUNs is either 512 KB, or 128 KB, depending on the file system the building block is intended for. A larger segment size implies that larger I/O requests can be handled by a single I/O operation at the controller level. But it also implies that an I/O request *must* be larger to optimally utilize the underlying disks fully in parallel. A segment size of 512 KB combined with a RAID6 scheme of $8+p+q$ results in a stripe size that is optimal for block device I/O of 4 MB (or multiples of thereof). 4 MB is indeed the file system block size of the “WORK” file system on JUGENE.

The aggregate bandwidth of the 72 LUNs is around 8.5 GB/s. This is easily handled by the total of the 24 FC4 point to point connections between servers and controller ports, which have a nominal capacity of 12 GB/s. So the sustainable bandwidth of a basic building block is 8.5 GB/s. As with most RAID systems, the performance of read and write operations is not entirely symmetric. The write operations tend to be somewhat slower.

Figure 5: A basic GPFS building block consisting of two DS5300 storage boxes hooked up to three p6 570 servers.

With 24 data servers 8 basic GPFS building blocks are constructed. Combined they offer a bandwidth of about 68 GB/s. On JUGENE three (classes of) file systems for user files are available: “WORK”, “HOME” and “ARCH”. “WORK” is the primary work space for jobs, “HOME” is for user home directories – job scripts, binaries, sources, etc. – and “ARCH” is a file system for archiving. “ARCH” should not be accessed directly by a batch jobs running on JUGENE. Files that have resided on an archive file system for a while will have been migrated to tape. Retrieval of migrated files will take about 3 hours per TB.

All three file system classes are built from the basic GPFS building blocks described above. Exactly half of all storage resources, four basic GPFS building blocks, have been used to implement a single “WORK” file system. Three of them are used to implement three “HOME” file systems – i.e.: one per “HOME” file system. And one is used to implement the online disk capacity of three “ARCH” file systems. Table 2 summarizes the aggregate performance maxima that follow from this setup, along with some other attributes of the file system.

Table 2: Aggregate file system performance maxima

file system	number of GPFS building blocks	storage back-end file system bandwidth	file server uplink network bandwidth	RAID6 LUN segment size	GPFS block size
WORK	4	34.0 GB/s	60 GB/s	512 KB	4 MB
HOME	1	8.5 GB/s	15 GB/s	128 KB	1 MB
ARCH	1/3	2.8 GB/s	5 GB/s	512 KB	2 MB

2. Strategies for improving I/O performance on JUGENE

Some general principles for doing efficient I/O may be obvious in the light of the organization of the I/O subsystem presented in the first section. To summarize:

- With regard to the I/O nodes:
 - Assignment of I/O nodes to compute nodes is static; the application itself should make sure that it uses all I/O nodes at disposal.
 - Furthermore, the application should balance the I/O transfers as evenly as possible over the available I/O nodes.
- With regard to the “WORK” file system:
 - The application should take file system characteristics into account, particularly the fact that there are no node local workspaces.
 - Furthermore, the application should pay attention to file system block size and alignment of data along block boundaries.

It is less obvious how to practically apply these principles, or what sort of improvement will be gained by the effort of adapting a program. One feasible strategy is to delegate this problem to a parallel I/O library. I.e.: a library that specifically offers routines for using a single file in collective actions of multiple tasks. But neither is it unfeasible to optimize I/O *without* using a parallel I/O library. Many existing user codes were designed to do “parallel I/O” only in the sense that several tasks, or even all tasks, access a file system concurrently – each task involved in I/O reading or writing its own file, while MPI communication is used to transport data to/from the I/O performing tasks to other tasks. For such codes this may be an attractive strategy that could limit the amount of code modifications.

In section 2.1, parallel I/O libraries available on JUGENE are listed and their different focuses are highlighted. The reference section contains references to websites that provide user documentation, including example programs, and sometimes reports discussing on performance improvements and other merits of the software. To test each of the libraries is beyond the scope of this paper. In section 2.2 some options for improving I/O without the use of parallel I/O libraries are explored. The merits of a BlueGene specific MPI extension for improving I/O are analyzed in detail and a code example of its usage is included.

2.1. Parallel I/O libraries

One strategy is for improving I/O by making use of a library that specifically offers routines for using a single file in collective actions by multiple tasks. The tasks engage in collectively opening a file and get a file handle in return that they can use in I/O operations for which the library offers its interface functions. The problem concurrently accessing the right part of the file for the right task and of doing this efficiently is delegated to the library implementation.

Parallel HDF [2] and Parallel NetCDF [3] are available on JUGENE. The primary focus of these libraries is organizing application output into portable, platform independent, formats. These libraries in turn are implemented on top of MPI I/O [4], a part of MPI-2 standard specifically introduced for dealing with parallel I/O. It offers routines that implement the opening, reading, writing, and closing of files as collective actions.

HDF, NetCDF, and MPI I/O introduce their own data types. MPI I/O files are lists of MPI data types. Basic types are pre-defined. Derived types can be tailored to suit the application’s needs. Usage of these features however does not automatically tune file system access. The tailored data types of MPI I/O that make sense to the application are not necessarily well aligned with respect to file system specific parameters. But MPI I/O can be “hinted”, rather than instructed, to be more efficient by using “MPI_info” key value pairs to specify desired buffer size, stripe size, etc.

Introduction of these libraries into existing codes may be fairly intrusive. But for applications that already use HDF or NetCDF, using the parallel versions is an obvious optimization path.

For other existing source codes a different approach, as taken by SIONlib [5], may be more feasible. SIONlib is a fairly small library that focuses more directly on performance tuning of massive parallel file access. “Under the hood” it uses MPI communication functions - not MPI I/O – to implement and manage opening and closing files as collective actions with standard POSIX I/O routines. SIONlib does not introduce its own data types. Its parallel open routine initializes pointers to file of the standard C variety: “FILE *”, which can subsequently be used by tasks in calls to standard C functions. Only a limited number of I/O calls has to be replaced by SIONlib alternatives. Introduction into existing source code therefore might be less intrusive. SIONlib primarily focuses on the file system. Internally SIONlib takes care of the orchestration of assignment of well aligned blocks within a file to each task.

2.2. *Optimizing I/O without using a parallel I/O library*

To provide a coding example in this area and at the same time get a fair estimate of what sort performance can be achieved along this path, four small and comparable test programs were written in C. Two of them are unoptimized base line models at the opposite ends of a spectrum. In the first baseline program, I/O is fully parallel and without any hierarchy, in that each task does its own I/O and uses its own task specific file. Thus, I/O is parallel, but not orchestrated as a collective action. The second baseline program I/O is hierarchical and completely serial, in that all tasks use MPI communication to route their I/O to a single task – usually the one with “MPI_COM_WORLD” rank 0 - which subsequently does all disk I/O. But models are not uncommon in existing user codes.

The remaining two programs are attempts at improving I/O throughput achieved, by adapting I/O transfers sizes to the file system block size where possible, and by seeking a parallel hierarchical organization that keeps a more sensible middle position on the continuum between the first two extremes. Parts of source listing of the latter two programs have been included in appendices below.

All four programs only use a combination of standard I/O and MPI communication, but no MPI I/O or other collective parallel I/O functionality from any library. One program, test program 4, uses a BlueGene specific MPI extension that brings information about the pset topology of underlying hardware into the application program. This information can be used to distributing the I/O transfer load evenly over all I/O nodes that happen to be at the jobs disposal. Since the optimizations tried here are not packaged with others in the implementation of a library, it is possible to get a good estimate of the impact – or lack of impact - of individual changes.

Each program was run on JUGENE, over different numbers of cores. All runs were done with parameters to produce a 32K record per task per checkpoint, to store such a record on JUGENE’s “WORK” file system, and to do so for 40 checkpoints. Thus, irrespective of the program used, all runs over 4096 cores produce an output volume of 5GB, all runs over 8192 cores produce an output volume of 10 GB, and all runs over 16384 cores produce an output volume of 20 GB. Every program was written to keep track of the time spent for opening and closing files, for writing data, and, if applicable, for gathering data. The tests have been conducted as batch jobs under normal production conditions. Because of this, every type of run was conducted several times and results are presented in terms of averages for each type of run.

2.2.1. *Test 1: Each task directly uses its own task specific file*

The first baseline program does nothing particular to optimize its I/O for JUGENE. Each task simply opens its own task-specific file, writes the first record at the first checkpoint, appends the second record at the second checkpoint, and so on, and finally closes the file after the last checkpoint. In fact this is not at all an unusual way for applications to organize their I/O. For applications developed on architectures like the “Beowulf” cluster of several years ago, in which each compute nodes has node local storage that is used as work space, it even is a straightforward way to use of all I/O resources at the jobs disposal. Even on the BlueGene architecture this organization at least makes sure that each I/O node is used, and probably, because all cores are forwarding to their statically determined I/O node, in a balanced way.

The model however has other problems. It disregards the fact that the “WORK” file system, as any other file system available on JUGENE, is a shared file system and a global name space for all tasks. A user typically has a single access point, a directory with write permission in the file system. So if a user application running on several thousands of cores creates thousands of files or directories under this single root, a hotspot for meta-data handling is created. Some requests will get immediately, but meanwhile many other requests are being queued. This effect is visible in the results presented in Table 3. With 16384 cores, the time needed for opening and closing files is at approximately 65% of the total I/O time. The absolute job throughput of 0.1961 GB/s is actually still slightly better than that of the runs over 8192 cores, but this 10.5% increase in throughput must handle a doubled I/O volume and is all that is achieved by using the double number of I/O nodes. The reduced efficiency stands out clearly by looking at the average throughput per task that is achieved.

The model of organization also has little room for optimizing the sizes of data transfers to the file system. Each task is basically doing I/O on its own. It just writes the size of its record and does not bother about the file system block size. Aggregating more task state records to a more suitable size, postponing I/O is often not an option – in the case of an actual application checkpointing its state, it would defy the purpose if the I/O.

Table 3: Test 1, each task does I/O, using its own task specific file, results for different numbers of cores/MPI tasks. In this test the spread of the I/O time of individual runs around their average was much wider than in the other tests. Therefore this table reports a \pm standard deviation value, below its associated mean, to appreciate the representativeness of the average.

Task Rec.	I/O Vol.	Cores/ Tasks	I/O Tasks	Runs	Total I/O time	open + close time	gather time	throughput, job	throughput, Avg. per task
KB	GB	#	#	#	s	% total I/O	% total I/O	GB/s	KB/s
32	5	4096	4096	10	64.78	40.69	N.A.	0.0849	21.73
					\pm 21.87	\pm 16.78			
32	10	8192	8192	11	57.65	44.19	N.A.	0.1775	22.72
					\pm 8.21	\pm 10.69			
32	20	16384	16384	9	103.28	64.99	N.A.	0.1961	12.55
					\pm 11.52	\pm 5.79			

2.2.2. Test 2: Only one tasks performs I/O on behalf of all others

In the second baseline program, only one task, the one with “MPI_COMM_WORLD” rank 0, actually does any disk I/O. It opens a single file. At each of the checkpoints each task produces its 32K record and all records are gathered by task 0. Task 0 subsequently writes them to file. Obviously the scaling potential to larger numbers of cores severely limited. With 8192 tasks and a 32K record per task, 256 MB is needed for the gather buffer, which is already half of the memory available per core. The time spent in the gather action is also likely to increase with an increased number of nodes.

Also obvious is that this model of I/O organization is a recipe for leaving idle all I/O nodes except one. When the program is scaled to run over higher numbers of cores, proportionally more I/O nodes are allocated to the job, but the task with rank 0 runs on one particular core and the cores is member of one particular pset. The I/O nodes of the other psets simply remain unused.

However, since one task is collecting all the data, in this model there is some room for improvement by taking the file system block size into account. The test results obtained for this model, with and without this improvement, are presented in Table 4.

Note that the total I/O time reported for test 2 contains a term that is not applicable, or zero, for test 1: viz. the time spent gathering data. The time spent in “MPI_Gather” is also included in the calculation of job throughput and average throughput per task. This is simply consistent with the fact that usage of this call is an intrinsic part of the organization of the I/O in test 2 program. The same applies to tests 3 and 4, of which the results are consequently also reported in this way. The time spent gathering is reported as a percentage of the total I/O time in the 8th table column, similar to the way in which the time spent on opening and closing (a) file(s) is reported in the 7th column. The bandwidth, in GB/s, utilized by the I/O node(s) on the I/O back-end in the narrow sense can hence be reconstructed by the following calculation:

$$\text{Utilized back-end bandwidth} = \text{I/O Vol.} / (\text{Total I/O time} * (1 - \text{gather time}/100))$$

E.g.: The first job throughput reported in Table 4, of 0.0721 GB/s, thus corresponds to a utilized back-end bandwidth of 0.0982 GB/s.

Table 4: A single task does all I/O on behalf of all others, results for different numbers of cores/MPI tasks

Task Rec.	I/O Vol.	Cores/ Tasks	I/O Tasks	Runs	Total I/O time	open + close time	gather time	throughput, job	throughput, Avg. per task
KB	GB	#	#	#	s	% total I/O	% total I/O	GB/s	KB/s
I/O transfers of task record size (32K)									
32	5	4096	1	8	69.36	0.19	26.55	0.0721	18.46
32	10	8192	1	5	138.76	0.07	26.53	0.0721	9.23
I/O transfers of (multiples) of file system block size									
32	5	4096	1	8	43.05	0.12	42.79	0.1163	29.77
32	10	8192	1	8	86.91	0.04	42.37	0.1152	14.75

The results show that doing I/O with the file system block size significantly improves the throughput achieved by the job and the average efficiency per task. But, quite surprisingly, choosing higher multiples - 2, 4, 8 or 16 – of the block size did *not* improve results any further. GPFS is a striped file system. When a GPFS client chooses larger write sizes, the multiple blocks to be used are normally allocated on multiple GPFS network storage devices. Larger I/O requests should in principle utilize a larger number of storage back-end devices in parallel and hence improve throughput. However this effect was not noticeable, hence probably not achieved, by the tests conducted here.

2.2.3. Test 3: A limited number of tasks performs I/O on behalf of others

The third test program on the one hand tries to avoid the meta-data hotspot effect of the first test and to avoid the complete serialization of I/O on the other hand, by grouping the total number of tasks in N-sized mutually exclusive subgroups. Only one task per subgroup performs I/O on behalf of all members of the group. The mutually exclusive subgroups are created as MPI communicators, by using “MPI_Comm_split” function on the “MPI_COMM_WORLD” communicator. The tasks ending up rank 0 in their subgroup communicator are appointed to be used as the root in the “MPI_Gather” calls on the subgroup communicator. Consult the annotated listing in appendix 3.1 for implementation details.

The subgroup size is a command line parameter for the test program. It is not at all a priori clear what a good size would be. Tests were run with subgroups of size 128, 256, and 512 cores. The results in Table 5 show that this model of I/O organisation leads in itself leads to substantially better throughput, even without bothering about the small sizes of the transfers used.

Subgroups of size 128 clearly work much better than using subgroups of 512 members, even though a pset of JUGENE has 512 members. This seeming oddity is at least partly explained by pointing out that the creation of subgroups in by test program 3 is systematic, but also based on a totally arbitrary criterion. The resulting *subgroups* do have an equal load of I/O work, but there still is no guarantee that all *I/O nodes* at the jobs disposal are used to share the load evenly. There is a possibility that two or more subgroups have ended up with a root node that is in the same pset and hence are sharing the same I/O node. With an equal amount of psets and subgroup root nodes, this would imply that one or more I/O nodes are left idle. The unlikely, but theoretically possible, worst case scenario would be that *all* subgroup root nodes are in fact member of the same pset: they would all be served by a single I/O node while all other I/O nodes allocated to the job are left idle. By using four times as many subgroups, but smaller ones, the probability of not using not using some I/O nodes of is reduced, as is the probability for the worst case scenario. The results in Table 5 also suggest that the time needed for gathering data might be shorter for four groups of 128 tasks than for 1 group of 512 tasks. But this in turn may very well vary with the topological characteristics of the tasks that end up in the same subgroup – which is unfortunately something over which test program 3 has no control.

Table 5: One task does I/O on behalf of all tasks in its subgroup, results for different numbers of cores/MPI tasks and different sizes of subgroups

Task Rec.	I/O Vol.	Cores/ Tasks	I/O Tasks	Runs	Total I/O time	open + close time	gather time	throughput, job	throughput, Avg. per task
KB	GB	#	#	#	s	% total I/O	% total I/O	GB/s	KB/s
32	5	4096	8	5	31.47	3.18	7.76	0.1681	43.03
32	5	4096	16	5	18.54	2.27	6.35	0.2747	70.32
32	5	4096	32	5	12.45	2.55	5.06	0.4370	111.87
32	10	8192	16	8	33.52	0.70	6.89	0.2984	38.20
32	10	8192	32	5	24.75	1.08	5.10	0.4409	56.44
32	10	8192	64	5	24.17	1.75	2.70	0.4662	59.67
32	20	16384	32	4	33.68	0.60	6.86	0.5940	38.02
32	20	16384	64	6	16.48	1.20	7.02	1.2136	77.67
32	20	16384	128	8	15.11	2.48	3.83	1.3240	84.74

2.2.4. Test 4: Hardware topology information “helps appointing” the limited number of tasks performing I/O on behalf of others

Rather than reducing the probability of not utilizing a particular resource, one would like to make absolutely sure that this is avoided. This however requires the use of pset topology information to assist in the formation of subgroups. This is what test program 4 does, by making use of an MPI call that is an BlueGene specific extension:

```
int MPIX_Pset_same_comm_create(MPI_Comm *pset_com);
```

This call is defined to be a collective action on the “MPI_COMM_WORLD” communicator such that in each task a communicator is returned that includes all tasks that run on cores that are served by the same I/O node.

The “work” functions of test program 3 and test program 4 do not differ a lot. Basically, the call to “MPI_Split_comm” in test program 3, to create communicators for subgroups, is replaced by a call to “MPIX_PSet_same_comm_create”. The size of the resulting communicators is the size of the pset and hence is implicitly taken as the size for the subgroups. Thus, when run for a small number of cores, on the rack of JUGENE that has 128 cores per pset, the program creates subgroups of 128 members. Consult the annotated source code listing in appendix 3.3 for more details.

The results presented in Table 6 show that this I/O organization model, when combined with “file system block size awareness”, scales very well up to job sizes of 64K cores, with very acceptable and roughly constant average throughput rates per task.

Table 6: One task does I/O of all other tasks that happen to run on cores in the same pset, results for different numbers of cores/MPI tasks

Task Rec.	I/O Vol.	Cores/ Tasks	I/O Tasks	Runs	Total I/O time	open + close time	gather time	throughput, job	throughput, Avg. per task
KB	GB	#	#	#	s	% total I/O	% total I/O	GB/s	KB/s
I/O transfers of task record size (32K)									
32	5	4096	8	5	10.03	10.81	22.81	0.5019	128.49
32	10	8192	16	8	9.46	3.79	24.13	1.0620	135.94
32	20	8192	32	6	9.66	6.66	23.69	2.0843	133.40
I/O transfers of (multiples) of file system block size									
32	5	4096	8	7	5.49	2.10	41.44	0.9118	233.42
32	10	8192	16	7	5.82	2.57	39.55	1.7411	222.86
32	20	16384	32	6	6.09	5.86	37.45	3.2957	210.92
32	40	32768	64	6	5.98	3.53	38.18	6.7205	215.06
32	80	65536	128	8	6.22	5.43	36.69	12.9571	207.31

For comparability of results with those of the other tests a task record size of 32K has been maintained. With test program 4, some tests have been conducted to corroborate that this I/O organization model also scales well when run with increased task record sizes. The results of these tests are presented in Table 7 and suggest that this is the case. If anything, the job throughput and average throughput per task even get slightly better with an increased I/O volume.

The gather time, as a percentage of the total I/O time, tends to increase only slightly, but the size of the gather buffer needed by the receiving tasks grows proportionally to the size of the task records. On JUGENE, which has a very modest amount of memory per core, this may be a problem, because the task will obviously need memory for computational purposes too.

Table 7: One task does I/O of all other tasks that happen to run on cores in the same pset, results for different numbers of cores/MPI tasks, and for different task records sizes/IO volumes

Task Rec.	I/O Vol.	Cores/ Tasks	I/O Tasks	Runs	Total I/O time	open + close time	gather time	throughput, job	throughput, Avg. per task
KB	GB	#	#	#	s	% total I/O	% total I/O	GB/s	KB/s
32	5	4096	8	7	5.63	4.01	40.47	0.8906	227.99
64	10	4096	8	7	13.26	2.79	35.57	0.7866	201.37
128	20	4096	8	7	23.21	0.92	39.24	0.8702	222.77
256	40	4096	8	7	43.72	0.40	41.23	0.9154	234.34
32	10	8192	16	6	6.08	4.82	37.77	1.6618	212.71
64	20	8192	16	6	11.92	1.40	38.12	1.6836	215.50
128	40	8192	16	6	22.02	1.57	40.98	1.8170	232.58

By directly using the “MPIX_Pset_same_comm_create” call, we have implicitly adopted the size of a pset for the number of task records that must be storable in the gather buffer of the receiving task. But there is no need for that. Once we have the pset information, it is fairly easy to construct evenly distributed subsets of members of the same pset. The following listing is an example of a “plug-and-play” substitute for “MPIX_Pset_same_comm_create”, which it uses internally, to create communicators for evenly distributed subsets of members of the same pset. To keep the call interface alike, a global variable “PSETDIVISOR” is used to decide how many subsets should be created. Like “MPIX_Pset_same_comm_create”, the wrapper function implicitly is a collective action on “MPI_COMM_WORLD” and must be called by all tasks.

```

void create_pset_subset_comm(MPI_Comm *io_commp)
{
    extern int PSETDIVISOR;
    MPI_Comm pset_comm;
    int pset_commrnk, io_comm_color;

    MPIX_Pset_same_comm_create(&pset_comm);
    MPI_Comm_rank(pset_comm, &pset_commrnk);

    /* Assign a "pset subset color", and split on the basis of that */
    io_comm_color = pset_commrnk % PSETDIVISOR;
    MPI_Comm_split(pset_comm, io_comm_color, 0, io_commp);
    MPI_Comm_free(&pset_comm); /* The comms for the complete pset are no longer needed
*/
}

```

Testing with this variation shows that there even is a gain in performance when the pset is divided into subgroups of 128 tasks. Why this is so, is not clear. There is not much improvement in the gather time. The gather time as a percentage of total I/O time increases, because the time spent writing decreases more. Apparently the I/O node of the pset can cope better with 4 chunks of 4MB concurrently forwarded by 4 compute nodes than with 1 chunk of 16MB forwarded by a single compute node. Is the I/O node very limited in forwarding larger requests? This would explain the earlier noted oddity, that writing with more blocks rather than with a single file system block, did not noticeably improve performance. This is odd, considering that GPFS file systems are striped file systems.

More than conjectures cannot be formulated here, as is it would require studying the I/O node’s internal behavior to come up with answers.

Table 8: One node per pset (512) doing I/O, versus 4 nodes per pset doing I/O

Task Rec.	I/O Vol.	Cores/ Tasks	I/O Tasks	Runs	Total I/O time	open + close time	gather time	throughput, job	throughput, Avg. per task
KB	GB	#	#	#	s	% total I/O	% total I/O	GB/s	KB/s
32	5	4096	8	7	5.49	2.10	41.44	0.9118	233.42
32	5	4096	32	8	3.98	4.29	46.55	1.2574	321.89
32	10	8192	16	7	5.82	2.57	39.55	1.7411	222.86
32	10	8192	64	8	4.16	6.07	44.74	2.4119	308.72
32	20	16384	32	6	6.09	5.86	37.45	3.2957	210.92
32	20	16384	128	8	4.28	7.22	44.28	4.7487	303.92

Conclusions

The I/O subsystem of the PRACE Tier-0 system JUGENE at Jülich has been dissected as a layered system and components and their interconnections have been described fairly in detail in the first section.

The second section explores to what organization of I/O among multiple tasks works best, or is at least efficient. Rather than adopting any particular library for parallel I/O, options open to any program that uses a combination of standard I/O and MPI are explored. Simply letting each task concurrently do its own standard I/O is adopted as a baseline model. This only results in an average per task throughput in the range 20-30 KB/s and drops even below that when scaling to 16384 tasks or more. Hierarchically organizing I/O within the program, splitting the tasks into a number of equally sized I/O groups, in which a few tasks do I/O on behalf of others in the same group improves performance, but only moderately, when group membership is essentially determined arbitrarily.

BlueGene specific MPI extensions have been used to bring topological information, about which tasks are being served by the same I/O node, into the program. Example source code listings are given on how these calls can be used to create a division into groups that are not only balanced in the IO/volume their produce, but also in the underlying resources they have at their disposal to handle the load. The test program that uses this information to hierarchically organize I/O in groups that actually correspond to psets in the underlying machine handles exactly the same I/O volume much more efficiently. When combined with a choice of an I/O transfer size equal to (multiples of) the file system block size, the achieved average per task is stably in the 200-230 KB/s range, even when scaled up to 65536 tasks.

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3. Appendices: Programming examples, annotated source listings

3.1. Annotated listing of the “work” function of test program 3

```
#include <stdlib.h>
#include <errno.h>
#include <mpi.h>

( . . . )

void work(void)
{
    FILE *fp;
    const char *workdir;
    const char *workfile;
    char *outbuff;
    char *gatherbuff;
    int i;
    double t0, t1, total_gathertime, opentime, closetime, writetime, total_writetime;

    MPI_Comm io_comm;          /* IO communicators, for mutually exclusive subgroups */
    int io_membership, io_rank, io_commsz;
    MPI_Comm io_rootcomm;     /* Communicator for all root nodes in IO communicator, convenient
                               for gathering and reporting statistics when the work is done.
                               */
    int is_iorootnode, io_rootrank, io_rootsz;

    errno = 0;
    if ((outbuff = malloc(OUTBUFFSZ)) == NULL) {
        errmsg(errno, "Task output buffer size (OUTBUFFSZ) should be at least 128 bytes!\n");
        MPI_Abort(MPI_COMM_WORLD, EXIT_FAILURE);
    }

    /* Assign IO membership "colors" for mutually exclusive subgroup membership and a rank
    within
       The subgroup on the basis of task rank in MPI_COMM_WORLD and the command line specified
       (max.) subgroup size.
    */
    io_membership = WORLDRANK / IOMEMBERMAX;
    io_rank = WORLDRANK % IOMEMBERMAX;
    MPI_Comm_split(MPI_COMM_WORLD, io_membership, io_rank, &io_comm);
    MPI_Comm_size(io_comm, &io_commsz);

    /* Tasks that have received rank 0 within an IO subgroup communicator are appointed
       root node. They will do the gathering and writing.
    */
    is_iorootnode = io_rank == 0 ? 1 : 0;
    MPI_Comm_split(MPI_COMM_WORLD, is_iorootnode, 0, &io_rootcomm);
    MPI_Comm_size(io_rootcomm, &io_rootsz);

    if (is_iorootnode) {
        workdir = init_workdir();
        workfile = init_workfile();
        fp = timed_open_workfile(workfile, "w", &opentime);
        errno = 0;
    }
}
```

```

    if ((gatherbuff = malloc(OUTBUFFSZ * io_commsz)) == NULL) {
        errmsg(errno, "Failed to allocate gather buffer\n");
        MPI_Abort(MPI_COMM_WORLD, EXIT_FAILURE);
    }
    total_gathertime = 0.0;
    total_writetime = 0.0;
}
else {
    MPI_Comm_free(&io_rootcomm);
}

if (NCHKPOINTS < 1) {
    errmsg(0, "Number of output producing checkpoints (NCHKPOINTS) should be at least 1!\n");
    MPI_Abort(MPI_COMM_WORLD, EXIT_FAILURE);
}

for(i = 0; i < NCHKPOINTS; i++) {
    produce_output_result(outbuff, OUTBUFFSZ);
    t0 = MPI_Wtime();
    MPI_Gather(outbuff, OUTBUFFSZ, MPI_CHAR, gatherbuff, OUTBUFFSZ, MPI_CHAR, 0, io_comm);
    t1 = MPI_Wtime();
    if (is_iorootnode) {
        char *p = gatherbuff;
        int j;
        total_gathertime += (t1 - t0);
        /* Still an unoptimized brain dead loop, resulting in exactly as many write calls
           as in the first test program. It calls the timed write routine for each
           received task record, rather than a few times for more size optimized chunks, or
           even just once for the complete gather buffer.
        */
        for (j = 0; j < io_commsz; j++) {
            timed_write_output_results(fp, p, OUTBUFFSZ, &writetime);
            total_writetime += writetime;
            p += OUTBUFFSZ;
        }
    }
}

if (is_iorootnode) {
    timed_close_workfile(fp, &closetime);
    report_statistics(io_rootcomm, io_commsz, opentime, closetime, total_writetime,
                    total_gathertime);
}
}

```

3.2. Annotated listing of “init_workdir” and “timed_write_outputresults” functions of test program 4.2

```

#include <stdlib.h>
#include <unistd.h>
#include <errno.h>
#include <sys/statvfs.h>
#include <mpi.h>
extern void errmsg(int errcode, char *fmt, ...);

( . . . )

```

```

const char *init_workdir(void)
/* Determine output destination directory and go there. Get the file system block size of
   file system. Store it, or a multiple thereof indicated by command line initialized global
   BLKMUL, in the global FSBLKSZ, to be used as norm for disk transfer size.
   Return a pointer to static (environment) memory containing the path to the destination
   directory.
*/
{
    struct vfs s;
    const char *wd = getenv("WORK");
    if (wd == NULL) {
        errmsg(0, "No value for environment variable \"WORK\"\n");
        MPI_Abort(MPI_COMM_WORLD, EXIT_FAILURE);
    }
    errno = 0;
    if (chdir(wd) != 0) {
        errmsg(errno, "Failed to change directory to \"%s\"\n", wd);
        MPI_Abort(MPI_COMM_WORLD, EXIT_FAILURE);
    }
    errno = 0;
    if (statvfs(".", &s) == 0) {
        FSBLKSZ = s.f_bsize * BLKMUL;
    }
    else {
        errmsg(errno, "Failed to obtain statvfs data on file system of \"%s\"\n", wd);
        MPI_Abort(MPI_COMM_WORLD, EXIT_FAILURE);
    }
    return wd;
}

void timed_write_output_results(FILE *fp, char *buff, size_t bufsize, double *sec)
{
    long i, n, rest;
    double t0, t1;

    n = bufsize / FSBLKSZ; /* Loop n times, writing FLBKSZ at a time */
    rest = bufsize % FSBLKSZ; /* Append a possible leftover */

    t0 = MPI_Wtime();
    errno = 0;
    for (i = 0; i < n; i++) {
        if (write(fileno(fp), buff + (i * FSBLKSZ), FSBLKSZ) != FSBLKSZ) {
            errmsg(errno, "Failed to write output to workfile\n");
            MPI_Abort(MPI_COMM_WORLD, EXIT_FAILURE);
        }
    }
    if (rest > 0) {
        if (write(fileno(fp), buff + (i * FSBLKSZ), rest) != rest) {
            errmsg(errno, "Failed to write output to workfile\n");
            MPI_Abort(MPI_COMM_WORLD, EXIT_FAILURE);
        }
    }
    t1 = MPI_Wtime();
    if (sec != NULL) {
        *sec = t1 - t0;
    }
}

```

3.3. Annotated listing of the “work” function of test program 4.2

```
#include <stdlib.h>
#include <errno.h>
#include <mpi.h>
#include <mpix.h>

( . . . )

Void work(void)
{
    FILE *fp;
    const char *workdir;
    const char *workfile;
    char *outbuff;
    char *gatherbuff;
    int i;
    double t0, t1, total_gathertime, opentime, closetime, writetime, total_writetime;
    MPI_Comm io_comm;
    int io_membership, io_rank, io_commsz;
    MPI_Comm io_rootcomm;
    int is_iorootnode, io_rootrank, io_rootsz;

    errno = 0;
    if ((outbuff = malloc(OUTBUFFSZ)) == NULL) {
        errmsg(errno, "Task output buffer size (OUTBUFFSZ) should be at least 128 bytes!\n");
        MPI_Abort(MPI_COMM_WORLD, EXIT_FAILURE);
    }
    MPIX_Pset_same_comm_create(&io_comm);
    MPI_Comm_size(io_comm, &io_commsz);
    MPI_Comm_rank(io_comm, &io_rank);

    is_iorootnode = io_rank == 0 ? 1 : 0;
    MPI_Comm_split(MPI_COMM_WORLD, is_iorootnode, 0, &io_rootcomm);
    MPI_Comm_size(io_rootcomm, &io_rootsz);
    if (is_iorootnode) {
        workdir = init_workdir();
        workfile = init_workfile();
        fp = timed_open_workfile(workfile, "w", &opentime);
        errno = 0;
        if ((gatherbuff = malloc(OUTBUFFSZ * io_commsz)) == NULL) {
            errmsg(errno, "Failed to allocate gather buffer\n");
            MPI_Abort(MPI_COMM_WORLD, EXIT_FAILURE);
        }
        total_gathertime = 0.0;
        total_writetime = 0.0;
    }
    else {
        MPI_Comm_free(&io_rootcomm);
    }
    if (NCHKPOINTS < 1) {
        errmsg(0, "Number of output producing checkpoints (NCHKPOINTS) should be at least 1!\n");
        MPI_Abort(MPI_COMM_WORLD, EXIT_FAILURE);
    }
    for(i = 0; i < NCHKPOINTS; i++) {
        produce_output_result(outbuff, OUTBUFFSZ);
        t0 = MPI_Wtime();
    }
}
```

```
MPI_Gather(outbuff, OUTBUFFSZ, MPI_CHAR, gatherbuff, OUTBUFFSZ, MPI_CHAR, 0, io_comm);
t1 = MPI_Wtime();
if (is_iorootnode) {
    total_gathertime += (t1 - t0);
    timed_write_output_results(fp, gatherbuff, io_commsz * OUTBUFFSZ, &writetime);
    total_writetime += writetime;
}
}
if (is_iorootnode) {
    timed_close_workfile(fp, &closetime);
    report_statistics(io_rootcomm, io_commsz, opentime, closetime, total_writetime,
                    total_gathertime);
}
}
```